

Synthesis and evaluation of Schiff bases and 4-thiazolidinones as antibacterial agents

Anjani N. Solankee

Department of Chemistry, B. K. M. Science College, Valsad-396 001, Gujarat, India

E-mail : dranjani_solankee@yahoo.com

Manuscript received 30 June 2010, revised 11 February 2011, accepted 26 May 2011

Abstract : 6-Methylpyridine-3-carbohydrazide (**2**) on condensation with different aromatic aldehydes (**1**) resulted in Schiff bases **3(a-i)**, which on cyclocondensation with thioglycolic acid resulted in 4-thiazolidinones **4(a-i)**. The newly synthesized compounds were characterized using IR, ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR and elemental analysis. Synthesized compounds were evaluated for their *in vitro* antibacterial activity against Gram-positive and Gram-negative strains.

Keywords : Schiff bases, 4-thiazolidinones, thioglycolic acid, antibacterial activity.

Introduction

The synthesis and assaying of biological potential of Schiff bases and 4-thiazolidinones have received considerable interest in the recently year¹⁻⁴. The nature of the substituent^{5,6} and its position⁷ in the molecule plays a vital role in determining the chemical and biological behaviours of Schiff bases and 4-thiazolidinones. Results of IR, ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR and spectral analysis confirmed the formation of the desired products.

Schiff bases have gained more importance because of their pharmacological activities such as anticancer⁸, anti-tubercular⁹ and fungicidal¹⁰. They have been frequently employed for medicinal use. Furthermore, the compounds containing 4-thiazolidinone ring exhibit a variety of biological activities such as antimicrobial¹¹, antitubercular¹², anti-inflammatory¹³, anthelmintic¹⁴, antidiabetic¹⁵, anti-HIV¹⁶, anticancer¹⁷ and anticonvulsant¹⁸. In view of above and in continuation of our work¹⁹ on Schiff bases and 4-thiazolidinones, we herein report a new series of Schiff bases **3(a-i)** and 4-thiazolidinones **4(a-i)**.

Results and discussion

The products **3(a-i)** and **4(a-i)** were characterized from spectral data and analytical data. The IR spectra of compounds **3(a-i)** reveals the presence of (-N=CH-) group (Schiff base moiety) by exhibiting strong absorption band in the region between 1630–1660 cm⁻¹. In IR spectra of compounds **4(a-i)** the presence of (C-S-C) group (4-

thiazolidinone moiety) showed absorption band in the region between 610–630 cm⁻¹. The ¹H NMR spectra of compounds **3(a-i)** (in CDCl₃) showed singlet of (-N=CH-) in the region of δ 8.3–8.6 ppm. In ¹H NMR spectra of compounds **4(a-i)** (in CDCl₃) showed the singlet of -CONH proton δ 9.0–9.5 ppm. The physical data also confirmed the synthesis of compounds **3(a-i)** and **4(a-i)**.

Antibacterial activity :

All the synthesised compounds were screened for their antibacterial activity were screened for their antibacterial activities against *S. aureus* (MTCC-96), *B. subtilis* (MTCC-441) (Gram-positive) and *E. coli* (MTCC-443), *S. paratyphi-B* (MTCC-733) (Gram-negative) bacteria using agar cup plate diffusion technique²⁰. The sterilized agar media [2.4% (w/v) agar-agar, 5% (w/v) NaCl, 3% (w/v) peptone, pH (6.8–7.0)] was poured into petri dishes and allowed to solidify. On the surface of the media, microbial suspension was spread over the agar plates to solidify. A stainless steel cylinder (pre-sterilized) was used to bore the cavities. All the synthesized compounds dissolved in DMF (100 µg/mL) were placed serially in the cavities with the help of micropipette. It was then allowed to diffuse for 10 min in a refrigerator. The plates were incubated at 37 °C for 24 h. After incubation, the diameter of zone of inhibition was measured in mm. Under similar conditions, controlled experiment was carried out by using ciprofloxacin as standard drug for comparison.

R = 2-NO₂, 3-NO₂, 2-OCH₃, 3-Br, 4-F, 4-*N,N*-(Me)₂, 4-*N,N*-(Et)₂, 3,4,5-(OCH₃)₃, cinnamyl

Reagents : (a) Toluene, reflux 6–7 h, (b) toluene, reflux 10–12 h, thioglycolic acid.

Table 1. Melting point and yields of compounds 3(a-i) and 4(a-i)

Compd.	R	M.p. (°C)	Yield (%)
3a	2-Nitrophenyl	211	79
3b	3-Nitrophenyl	200	80
3c	2-Methoxyphenyl	190	68
3d	3-Bromophenyl	135	70
3e	4-Flouorophenyl	192	65
3f	4- <i>N,N</i> -Dimethylphenyl	171	72
3g	4- <i>N,N</i> -Diethylphenyl	150	59
3h	3,4,5-Trimethoxyphenyl	125	74
3i	Cinnamyl	194	76
4a	2-Nitrophenyl	190	62
4b	3-Nitrophenyl	103	67
4c	2-Methoxyphenyl	165	59
4d	3-Bromophenyl	108	65
4e	4-Flouorophenyl	99	72
4f	4- <i>N,N</i> -Dimethylphenyl	68	78
4g	4- <i>N,N</i> -Diethylphenyl	65	69
4h	3,4,5-Trimethoxyphenyl	105	66
4i	Cinnamyl	97	60

A series of compounds Schiff bases and 4-thiazolidinones were prepared and tested for their *in vitro* antibacterial activity against the four strains of bacteria (Gram +ve, Gram -ve). In case of Gram +ve bacteria substitution of diethyl group at 4th position increase antibacterial activity of compounds in both series. In case of Gram -ve bacteria substitution of nitro group at 2nd position increase activity against *E. coli* (MTCC-443).

Experimental

All chemicals were of analytical grade and used directly. All the melting points were determined in an open capillary and are uncorrected. The completion of the reaction was monitored by thin layer chromatography (TLC) using silica gel-G coated Al-plates and spots were visualized under UV radiation. The infrared spectra were recorded on a Nicolet Impact-410 FT-IR spectrophotometer using KBr pallets. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker Advance DPX 400 MHz spectrophotometer using CDCl₃ as solvent and TMS as internal reference (Chemical shift in δ ppm).

Table 2. Antimicrobial activity of the compounds 3(a-i) and 4(a-i)

Compd.	R	Antibacterial activity (Zone of inhibition in mm)			
		<i>S. aureus</i> (MTCC-96)	<i>B. subtilis</i> (MTCC-441)	<i>E. coli</i> (MTCC-443)	<i>S. paratyphi-B</i> (MTCC-96)
3a	2-Nitrophenyl	16	13	17	-
3b	3-Nitrophenyl	17	14	15	10
3c	2-Methoxyphenyl	10	10	13	10
3d	3-Bromophenyl	13	13	14	10
3e	4-Flourophenyl	15	14	15	15
3f	4- <i>N,N</i> -Diethylphenyl	10	14	14	12
3g	4- <i>N,N</i> -Dimethylphenyl	18	20	15	14
3h	3,4,5-Trimethoxyphenyl	12	13	16	16
3i	Cinnamyl	15	14	14	13
4a	2-Nitrophenyl	-	15	17	12
4b	3-Nitrophenyl	-	14	17	11
4c	2-Methoxyphenyl	-	14	17	14
4d	3-Bromophenyl	14	-	17	15
4e	4-Flourophenyl	12	10	13	15
4f	4- <i>N,N</i> -Dimethylphenyl	14	15	13	10
4g	4- <i>N,N</i> -Diethylphenyl	19	19	13	10
4h	3,4,5-Trimethoxyphenyl	10	19	12	16
4i	Cinnamyl	20	16	13	11
Standard drug : Ciprofloxacin		22	21	24	25

Table 3. Minimum inhibitory concentration of the compounds 3(a-i) and 4(a-i)

Compd.	R	Minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC µg/ml)			
		<i>S. aureus</i> (MTCC-96)	<i>B. subtilis</i> (MTCC-441)	<i>E. coli</i> (MTCC-443)	<i>S. paratyphi-B</i> (MTCC-96)
3a	2-Nitrophenyl	12.5	25	25	-
3b	3-Nitrophenyl	25	12.5	-	6.25
3c	2-Methoxyphenyl	3.125	6.25	6.25	3.125
3d	3-Bromophenyl	50	25	12.5	25
3e	4-Flourophenyl	25	6.25	12.5	-
3f	4- <i>N,N</i> -Dimethylphenyl	50	50	100	50
3g	4- <i>N,N</i> -Diethylphenyl	50	25	6.25	50
3h	3,4,5-Trimethoxyphenyl	50	25	12.5	25
3i	Cinnamyl	100	> 125	> 125	-
4a	2-Nitrophenyl	100	-	50	25
4b	3-Nitrophenyl	-	50	25	50
4c	2-Methoxyphenyl	3.125	6.25	6.25	3.125
4d	3-Bromophenyl	50	-	-	25
4e	4-Flourophenyl	25	12.5	25	6.25
4f	4- <i>N,N</i> -Dimethylphenyl	50	25	6.25	50
4g	4- <i>N,N</i> -Diethylphenyl	50	25	12.5	25
4h	3,4,5-Trimethoxyphenyl	25	50	50	25
4i	Cinnamyl	12.5	25	25	-
Standard Drug : Ciprofloxacin		6.25	12.5	12.5	3.125

Minimal inhibitory concentration (MIC) :

The antibacterial activity was assayed *in vitro* by the broth dilution against antibacterial activity against *S. aureus* (MTCC-96), *B. subtilis* (MTCC-441) [Gram-positive bacteria] and *E. coli* (MTCC-443), *S. paratyphi-B* (MTCC-733) [Gram-negative bacteria]. Minimal inhibitory concentration (MIC $\mu\text{g/ml}$) were define by lowest concentration of compound that was completely inhibited the growth of each strain. All the compounds dissolved dimethyl formamide, were added culture media. Mueller Hinton broth for bacteria and sabouraud liquid medium for bacteria to obtained final concentration raging from 200.000–1.592 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. The amount of dimethyl formamide 1% v/v inoculate consisted of 1×10^3 bac/ml. The MIC were read after inoculation at 30 °C for 48 h. Media and media with 1% v/v dimethyl formamide were employed as growth controls. Ciprofloxacin were used as references antibacterial drugs. To detect type of antibacterial activity sub culture were performed by transferring 100 μL of each mixture remaining clear in 1 ml of fresh medium. The minimum bactericidal concentration were read after incubation at 37 °C for 24 h and at 30 °C for 48 h.

General preparation of N-(substituted benzylidene/cinnamylidene)-6-methylpyridin-3-carbonylhydrazone 3(a-i) : Mixture of 6-methylpyridine-3-carboxyhydrazide (0.01 mol) and different aromatic aldehydes (0.01 mol) were refluxed on water bath using Dean-Stark as water separator for 6–7 h in dry toluene. Excess of toluene was then distilled off and resulting products were recrystallised from alcohol.

(3a) : IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 1677 (C=O), 1648 (-N=CH-), 3455 (-NH str.), 1545 (C-NO₂); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 2.5 (3H, s, CH₃), 7.00–9.00 (7H, m, Ar-H), 8.4 (s, -N=CH-), 11.80 (1H, s, -CONH); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) : 23.9(1), 124.0(1), 125.4(1), 126.6(1), 128.4(1), 130.1(1), 131.9(1), 134.9(1), 137.2(1), 143.3(1), 147.8(1), 153.3(1), 159.4(1), 163.2(1) (Found : C, 59.10; H, 4.22; N, 19.67. Calcd. for C₁₄H₁₂N₄O₃ : C, 59.15; H, 4.25; N, 19.71%).

(3b) : IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 1675 (C=O), 1642 (-N=CH-), 3459 (-NH str.), 1552 (C-NO₂); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 2.53 (3H, s, -CH₃), 7.10–9.10 (7H, m, Ar-H), 8.42 (s, -N=CH-), 11.86 (1H, s, -CONH); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) : 23.9(1), 121.6(1), 125.4(1), 126.2(2), 129.7(1), 132.5(1), 134.6(1), 137.2(1), 146.8(1), 148.1(1), 153.3(1), 159.4(1),

163.2(1) (Found : C, 59.09; H, 4.20; N, 19.68. Calcd. for C₁₄H₁₂N₄O₃ : C, 59.15; H, 4.25; N, 19.71%).

(3c) : IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 1259 (C–O–C), 1670 (C=O), 1649 (-N=CH-), 3452 (-N–H str.); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 2.55 (3H, s, -CH₃), 7.15–9.15 (7H, m, Ar-H), 8.49 (s, -N=CH-), 11.79 (1H, s, -CONH), 3.90 (3H, s, -OCH₃); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) : 23.9(1), 55.8(1), 111.2(1), 116.9(1), 121.1(1), 125.4(1), 126.6(1), 131.7(1), 132.0(1), 137.2(1), 146.0(1), 153.3(1), 157.6(1), 159.4(1), 163.2(1) (Found : C, 66.84; H, 5.55; N, 15.12. Calcd. for C₁₅H₁₅N₃O₂ : C, 66.90; H, 5.61; N, 15.16%).

(3d) : IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 1673 (C=O), 1645 (-N=CH-), 3451 (-N–H str.), 590 (C–Br); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 2.49 (3H, s, -CH₃), 7.05–9.05 (7H, m, Ar-H), 8.46 (s, -N=CH-), 11.88 (1H, s, -CONH); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) : 23.9(1), 123.2(1), 125.4(1), 126.6(1), 128.2(1), 132.7(1), 133.9(1), 135.9(1), 137.2(1), 146.8(1), 153.3(1), 159(1), 163.2(1) (Found : C, 52.80; H, 3.76; N, 13.15. Calcd. for C₁₄H₁₂N₃OBr : C, 52.85; H, 3.80; N, 13.21%).

(3e) : IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 1678 (C=O), 1651 (-N=CH-), 3449 (-N–H str.), 1010 (C–F); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 2.56 (3H, s, -CH₃) 7.00–9.00 (7H, m, Ar-H), 8.44 (s, -N=CH-), 11.82 (1H, s, -CONH); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) : 23.9(1), 115.6(2), 125.4(1), 126.6(1), 129.3(1), 130.8(1), 137.2(1), 146.8(1), 153.3(1), 159.4(1), 163.2(1), 165.2(1) (Found : C, 65.32 ; H, 4.64; N, 16.28. Calcd. for C₁₄H₁₂N₃OF : C, 65.36 ; H, 4.70; N, 16.33%).

(3f) : IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 1672 (C=O), 1647 (-N=CH-), 3453 (-N–H str.); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 2.50 (3H, s, -CH₃), 2.90 (6H, N-(CH₃)₂), 7.20–9.20 (7H, m, Ar-H), 8.42 (s, -N=CH-), 11.89 (1H, s, -CONH); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) : 23.9(1), 41.3(2), 111.9(2), 123.2(1), 125.4(1), 126.6(1), 128.3(2), 137.2(1), 146.8(1), 153.3(1), 153.4(1), 159.4(1), 163.2(1) (Found : C, 68.03; H, 6.38; N, 19.79. Calcd. for C₁₆H₁₈N₄O : C, 68.07; H, 6.42; N, 19.84%).

(3g) : IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 1678 (C=O), 1649 (-N=CH-), 3458 (-N–H str.); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 1.15 (6H, t, (CH₂-CH₃)₂), 2.57 (3H, s, -CH₃), 4.1 (4H, q, (CH₂-CH₃)₂), 7.10–9.10 (7H, m, Ar-H), 8.40 (s, -N=CH-), 11.80 (1H, s, -CONH); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) : 12.9(2), 23.9(1), 47.1(2), 111.9(2), 123.2(1), 125.4(1), 126.6(1), 128.3(2), 137.2(1), 146.8(1), 148.8(1), 153.3(1), 159.4(1), 163.2(1) (Found : C, 69.60; H, 7.37; N, 18.00. Calcd. for C₁₈H₂₂N₄O : C, 69.66; H, 7.41; N, 18.05%).

(3h) : IR (KBr) (cm^{-1}) : 1680 (C=O), 1645 (-N=CH-), 3456 (-N-H str.), 1037 (C-O-C str.); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) : δ 2.48 (3H, s, -CH₃), 3.75 (6H, s, *m*-OCH₃), 3.80 (3H, s, *p*-OCH₃), 6.90-8.90 (7H, m, Ar-H), 8.4 (s, -N=CH-), 11.82 (1H, s, -CONH); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3) : 23.9(1), 56.1(1), 60.8(1), 104.0(1), 125.4(1), 126.6(1), 128.0(1), 137.2(1), 141.5(1), 146.8(1), 153.2(2), 153.3(1), 159.4(1), 163.2(1) (Found : C, 61.96; H, 5.77; N, 12.71. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{19}\text{N}_4\text{O}$: C, 62.00; H, 5.81; N, 12.76%).

(3i) : IR (KBr) (cm^{-1}) : 1678 (C=O), 1650 (-N=CH-), 3454 (-N-H str.); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) : δ 2.54 (3H, s, -CH₃), 6.6 (1H, d, Ar-CH=, *J* 16 Hz), 7.25-8.95 (7H, m, Ar-H), 8.05 (1H, d, CH=, *J* 16 Hz), 8.49 (s, -N=CH-), 11.80 (1H, s, -CONH); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3) : 23.9(1), 125.4(1), 126.3(1), 126.6(1), 128.5(2), 128.6(2), 127.9(1), 134.1(1), 135.2(1), 137.2(2), 153.3(1), 159.4(1), 163.2(1) (Found : C, 53.58; H, 3.88; N, 15.56. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_3\text{O}$: C, 53.63; H, 3.93; N, 15.63%).

General preparation of 2-(substituted phenyl/cinnamyl)-3-(6'-methylpyridine-3'-carboxamido)-4-thiazolidinones 4(a-i) : A mixture of Schiff base **3(a-i)** (0.01 mol) and thioglycolic acid (0.01 mol) in dry toluene (60 ml) was refluxed on water bath using Dean-Stark water separator for 10-12 h. Excess of toluene was then distilled off and the resulting viscous liquid was treated with saturated NaHCO_3 solution to remove unreacted thioglycolic acid. The resulting product separated was washed with water, dried and recrystallized from alcohol.

(4a) : IR (KBr) (cm^{-1}) : 1677 (C=O), 3455 (-NH), 1370 (-C=N-), 1545 (C-NO₂), 614 (C-S-C); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) : δ 2.5 (3H, s, -CH₃), 3.75 (2H, q, -CH₂), 7.10-8.70 (7H, m, Ar-H), 9.0 (1H, s, -CONH); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3) : 23.9(1), 59.7(1), 124.8(1), 125.4(1), 126.6(1), 128.1(1), 129.6(1), 133.4(1), 134.7(1), 137.2(1), 149.1(1), 153.3(1), 159.4(1), 164.4(1), 168.8(1) (Found : C, 53.57; H, 3.88; N, 15.59. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_4\text{O}_4\text{S}$: C, 53.63; H, 3.93; N, 15.63%).

(4b) : IR (KBr) (cm^{-1}) : 1677 (C=O), 3452 (-N-H), 1372 (-C=N-), 1545 (C-NO₂), 620 (C-S-C); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) : δ 2.53 (3H, s, -CH₃), 3.78 (2H, q, -CH₂), 7.15-8.75 (7H, m, Ar-H), 9.15 (1H, s, -CONH); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3) : 23.9(1), 35.6(1), 63.3(1), 122.3(1), 125.1(1), 125.4(1), 126.6(1), 129.5(1), 133.0(1), 137.2(1), 140.1(1), 147.8(1), 153.3(1), 159.4(1), 164.8(1), 168.8(1)

(Found : C, 53.57; H, 3.88; N, 15.57. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_4\text{O}_4\text{S}$: C, 53.63; H, 3.93; N, 15.63%).

(4c) : IR (KBr) (cm^{-1}) : 1675 (C=O), 3455 (-N-H), 1370 (-C=N-), 1260 (C-O-C), 618 (C-S-C); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) : δ 2.50 (3H, s, -CH₃), 3.75 (3H, s, -OCH₃), 3.72 (2H, q, -CH₂), 7.20-8.80 (7H, m, Ar-H), 9.20 (1H, s, -CONH); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3) : 23.9(1), 35.6(1), 56.1(1), 58.4(1), 112.2(1), 116.5(1), 120.9(1), 125.5(1), 126.6(1), 127.6(1), 128.1(1), 137.2(1), 153.3(1), 158.3(1), 159.4(1), 164.8(1), 168.8(1) (Found : C, 59.40; H, 4.93; N, 12.17. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_3\text{O}_3\text{S}$: C, 59.46; H, 4.99; N, 12.24%).

(4d) : IR (KBr) (cm^{-1}) : 1677 (C=O), 3450 (-N-H-), 1378 (-C=N-), 610 (C-Br), 631 (C-S-C); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) : δ 2.53 (3H, s, -CH₃), 3.77 (2H, q, -CH₂), 7.25-8.75 (7H, m, Ar-H); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3) : 23.9(1), 35.6(1), 63.6(1), 123.0(1), 125.4(1), 125.9(1), 126.6(1), 129.4(1), 130.0(1), 133.5(1), 137.2(1), 141.4(1), 153.3(1), 159.4(1), 164.8(1), 168.8(1) (Found : C, 48.94; H, 3.54; N, 10.68. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_3\text{O}_2\text{SBr}$: C, 48.99; H, 3.59; N, 10.71%).

(4e) : IR (KBr) (cm^{-1}) : 1677 (C=O), 1642 (-N=CH-), 3445 (-N-H-), 1371 (-C=N-), 1015 (C-F), 639 (C-S-C); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) : δ 2.53 (3H, s, -CH₃), 3.78 (2H, q, -CH₂), 7.15-8.75 (7H, m, Ar-H), 8.42 (s, -N=CH-), 9.15 (1H, s, -CONH); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3) : 23.9(1), 35.6(1), 64.3(1), 115.4(2), 125.4(1), 126.6(1), 130.3(2), 134.8(1), 137.2(1), 153.3(1), 159.4(1), 161.3(1), 164.8(1), 168.8(1) (Found : C, 57.93; H, 4.19; N, 12.61. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_3\text{O}_2\text{SF}$: C, 58.00; H, 4.25; N, 12.68%).

(4f) : IR (KBr) (cm^{-1}) : 1677 (C=O), 3449 (-N-H-), 1374 (-C=N-), 615 (C-S-C); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) : δ 2.53 (3H, s, -CH₃), 2.82 (6H, s, N-(CH₃)₂), 3.80 (2H, q, -CH₂), 7.05-8.65 (7H, m, Ar-H), 9.1 (1H, s, -CONH); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3) : 23.9(1), 35.6(1), 41.3(1), 64.3(1), 112.8(2), 125.4(1), 126.6(1), 127.4(2), 128.7(1), 137.7(1), 149.5(1), 153.3(1), 159.4(1), 164.8(1), 168.8(1) (Found : C, 60.60; H, 5.59; N, 15.67. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_4\text{O}_2\text{S}$: C, 60.66; H, 5.65; N, 15.72%).

(4g) : IR (KBr) (cm^{-1}) : 1677 (C=O), 3455 (-N-H-), 1379 (-C=N-), 620 (C-S-C); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) : δ 1.15 (6H, t, (CH₂-CH₃)₂), 2.51 (3H, s, -CH₃), 3.78 (2H, q, -CH₂), 84.1 (4H, q, (CH₂-CH₃)₂), 7.10-8.90 (7H, m, Ar-H), 9.12 (1H, s, -CONH); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3) : 12.9(1), 23.9(1), 35.6(1), 47.1(1), 64.3(1), 112.8(2), 125.4(1),

126.6(1), 127.4(1), 128.7(1), 137.2(1), 148.0(1), 153.3(1), 159.4(1), 164.8(1), 168.6(1) (Found : C, 62.42 ; H, 6.25; N, 14.50. Calcd. for C₂₀H₂₄N₄O₂S : C, 62.48; H, 6.29; N, 14.57%).

(4h) : IR (KBr) (cm⁻¹) : 1679 (C=O), 3456 (-N-H), 1373 (-C=N-), 1265 (C-O-C), 635 (C-S-C); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 2.59 (3H, s, -CH₃), 3.78 (6H, s, *m*-OCH₃), 3.80 (3H, s, *p*-OCH₃), 3.84 (2H, q, -CH₂), 7.15–8.75 (7H, m, Ar-H), 9.18 (1H, s, -CONH); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) : 16.3(1), 19.4(1), 23.9(1), 35.6(1), 64.9(1), 125.4(1), 126.6(1), 127.5(1), 134.2(1), 136.0(1), 136.6(1), 137.2(1), 153.3(1), 159.4(1), 164.8(1), 168.8(1) (Found : C, 56.50; H, 5.19; N, 10.38. Calcd. for C₁₉H₂₁N₃O₅S : C, 56.57; H, 5.24; N, 10.42%).

(4i) : IR (KBr) (cm⁻¹) : 1668 (C=O), 3445 (-N-H), 1384 (-C=N-), 625 (C-S-C); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 2.50 (3H, s, -CH₃), 3.79 (2H, q, -CH₂), 7.15–8.85 (7H, m, Ar-H), 9.15 (1H, s, -CONH); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) : 23.9(1), 36.1(1), 57.9(1), 123.3(1), 125.4(1), 126.6(1), 127.9(1), 128.6(4), 129.5(1), 137.2(1), 153.3(1), 159.4(1), 164.8(1), 168.8(1) (Found : C, 6.66; H, 4.98; N, 12.30. Calcd. for C₁₈H₁₇N₃O₂S : C, 63.70; H, 5.04; N, 12.38%).

Acknowledgement

Author is grateful to B. K. M. Science College, Valsad for providing research facilities and to Microbiology Department for carrying out antibacterial activity. Atul Ltd. (Atul) for the IR spectral analysis and G.V.K. Bioscience Pvt. Ltd. (Hyderabad) for the ¹H NMR spectral analysis.

References

1. C. Guang-Ming and H. C. Brown, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2000, **122**, 4217.
2. H. G. Hahn, K. D. Nam and H. Mah, *Heterocyclics*, 2001, **55**, 1283.
3. Upma, J. R. Sharma and M. R. Manrao, *Indian J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 2004, **14**, 177.
4. R. K. Sandhar, J. R. Sharma and M. R. Manrao, *Pestic. Res. J.*, 2005, **17**, 9.
5. M. R. Manrao, R. K. Sethi, R. C. Sharma and S. Kalsi, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1996, **73**, 695.
6. M. R. Manrao, K. K. Gill, J. R. Sharma and S. Kalsi, *Indian J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 1995, **5**, 85.
7. M. R. Manrao, M. Jolly, J. R. Sharma and P. S. Kalsi, *Pestic. Res. J.*, 1996, **8**, 13.
8. I. D. Modi, S. S. Sabnis and C. V. Deliwala, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1970, **13**, 933.
9. L. Muslin, W. Roth and H. Erlenmeyer, *Helv. Chem. Acta*, 1953, **36**, 886.
10. N. P. Das and A. S. Mittra, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, **55**, 907.
11. C. G. Bonde and N. J. Gaikwad, *Bioorg. Med. Chem.*, 2004, **12**, 2151.
12. S. G. Kucukguzel, E. E. Oruc, S. Rollas, F. Sachin and A. Ozbek, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 2002, **7**, 197.
13. B. Goel, T. Ram, R. Tyagi, E. Bansal, A. Kumar, D. Mukherjee and J. N. Sinha, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 1999, **34**, 265.
14. S. K. Srivastava, R. Yadav and S. D. Srivastava, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 2004, **43**, 399.
15. N. J. Gaikwad and P. Gautam, *Indian J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 2002, **12**, 181.
16. A. Rao, J. Balzarini, A. Carbone, A. Chimirri, E. D. Clercq, A. M. Monforte, P. Monforte, C. Pannecouque and M. Zappala, *Antiviral. Res.*, 2004, **63**, 79.
17. V. Gududuru, E. Hurh, J. T. Dalton and D. Miller, *Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett.*, 2004, **14**, 5289.
18. N. J. Gaikwad, M. Yunus, H. A. Husain and D. B. Meshram, *Indian J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 2002, **12**, 165.
19. A. Solankee, K. Kapadia, Y. Prajapati, H. Patel, P. Solankee and S. Solankee, *Acta Ciencia Indica*, 2007, **33**, C(4) 481.
20. A. Barry, "The Antimicrobial Susceptibility Test : Principal and Practice", Illus, Lea & Febiger, Philadelphia, Pa, USA, 1976, 180.